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KINESTHETIC LEARNING IN THE ESL CLASSROOM

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Abstract. *This paper discusses the use of kinesthetic learning with the purpose of improving students' engagement on the lesson in the classroom of learning English as a second language. There are many forms of learning, among which one could feature visual, auditory, reading and writing learning styles, applying which is especially effective for some students and not the most appropriate for others depending on the way they perceive information and materials the best. Based on our experience of working with students of higher education and utilizing kinesthetic form of learning on the lessons aimed at learning English as a second language, we would like to demonstrate our view on the matter, as well as provide some approaches one could use on the lessons for developing English with the assistance of kinesthetic style of learning.*

Keywords: *kinesthetic learning, ESL, English language, learning styles, learning styles.*

Introduction

Modern learning conditions require teacher to operate unconventionally, that is, to acquaint themselves with relevant learning techniques, conduct tasks stimulating students' inventiveness and imagination. Considerable amount of attention goes to visual, auditory, reading and writing aspects during the lessons aimed at development of English language. Nonetheless, not enough of focus is directed on kinesthetic learning in the classroom for learning a second language.

Kinesthetic learning requires students to learn through the process of creating. Its essence lies in learners engaging in physical activities and hands-on experiences, while activating several senses at the same time, including touch, proprioception, and visual-spatial awareness. As a result, this form of learning stimulates the encoding and retrieval of information, given that the brain is able to process more efficiently and fixate the learning material through the utilization of different sensory inputs [1].

We find the given form of learning considerably effective, as passively studying something or performing standard tasks may not always be the most optimal variant for learners, keeping in mind that students' attention can gradually decrease during the course of a lesson consisting of numerous exercises or lengthy tasks, paired with amount of theoretical material at hand for them to examine.

Utilizing our experience working with university students of a linguistic degree program, we determined to apply kinesthetic learning in the classroom of learning English as a second language to discover its effectiveness or, on the contrary, the lack of it.

Methods

Before we began our research on the matter, we conducted a survey to gather information on students' thoughts on learning styles, emphasizing the kinesthetic form. The number of participants consisted of 17 students.

The first question aimed at discovering students' view on the most uncomplicated learning form.

Table 1. Voting results of the survey's first question

Which learning style is the most uncomplicated, in your view?				
Visual	Auditory	Kinesthetic	Reading	Writing
6 students (35.29%)	3 students (17.65%)	1 student (5.88%)	6 students (35.29%)	1 student (5.88%)

From the table above one can see that visual and reading forms of studying are seen as the most manageable types of learning, with 35.29% voting for the visual form and the same number of learners voting for the reading style of studying.

Our second question targeted students' lack of preference for either of the learning styles, accentuating their personal perspective in terms of their studying.

Table 2. Voting results of the survey's second question

Which learning style isn't preferable for you personally?				
Visual	Auditory	Kinesthetic	Reading	Writing
2 students (11.76%)	2 students (11.76%)	1 student (5.88%)	5 students (29.41%)	7 students (41.18%)

The results demonstrate that writing is not considered as the most preferable learning form from the students' viewpoint, with the reading form being the close second based on the percentages in the results.

Our third question aimed at examining which learning style the students demonstrate an interest in utilizing more frequently.

Table 3. Voting results of the survey's third question

Applying more of which learning style would you feel an interest in?				
Visual	Auditory	Kinesthetic	Reading	Writing
1 student (5.88%)	3 students (17.65%)	10 students (58.82%)	2 students (11.76%)	1 student (5.88%)

Based on the numbers of percentages, one can conclude that the learning style the students feel an incentive to apply more on the lessons aimed at studying English as a second language, are kinesthetic and auditory, with 58.82% of the learners voting for the kinesthetic form and 17.65% of the students voting for the auditory style.

The survey results illustrated the necessity of continuing the research on the matter, actively utilizing kinesthetic form of learning in the classroom. To monitor students' progress and attitudes during the process, we applied observation to subsequently infer on the efficiency of the given learning style.

To monitor students' progress, we used observation for 4 weeks of applying kinesthetic learning in the classroom. Furthermore, with the purpose of not relying on observation only, we conducted a pre-test consisting of 30 questions, targeting lexical, grammar knowledge of the students, as well as auditory and reading skills on the set of themes as Communication, Housing and Living, Appearances, Sports and Media.

Results of the pre-test may be examined from the table below:

Table 4. Results of the pre-test

ST1	25
ST2	17
ST3	15
ST4	28
ST5	16
ST6	14
ST7	20
ST8	18
ST9	17
ST10	27
ST11	15
ST12	21
ST13	24
ST14	18
ST15	20
ST16	19

ST17	24
The average number of points	19,88

The purpose of the conducted pre-test is to further organize a post-test and compare the quantitative results of the learners to conclude whether the use of the kinesthetic approach increases efficiency of the lessons through a possibly heightened engagement of the students during class. As we can see from the table below, knowledge levels of the learners vastly differ from each other, with the average result being 19,88 points.

Discussion

In kinesthetic learning, students learn by moving and doing [2]. Considering that the issue at hand is not studied enough for the existence of a collection of appropriate activities available for use in the classroom for learning English as a second language, there was a necessity of composing such tasks independently and gather separate resources and materials individually.

The process of preparing lessons aimed at utilizing kinesthetic form of studying is rather compelling for the teachers themselves, as it requires lecturers to scrutinize a theme or a grammar rule under unusual angles for them to create tasks appropriate for the given style of learning.

The first sample of a possible use of kinesthetic learning in the English classroom is working with modelling clay. The connection between the mentioned unconventional object with a conventional English lesson may be understood through the number of ways it may be used for learning. Examining vocabulary to expand one's lexical knowledge may be a complicated task for some – lecturers frequently use some visual assistance to make it easier for learners to capture the word in their mind. However, if one is using kinesthetic studying form, the approach could include working with modelling clay. Students may learn the new lexical units by creating figurines, associations, objects, based on the meaning of the new words, not necessarily creating an accurate replica, but rather composing a substance which reminds them of the word. The combination of play, creativity and learning is rather effective in the space of learning English as a second language.

When we provided students with the described task, we could see students' heightened incentive and interest towards the lesson, with that, as a result, leading to an increased involvement on the lesson, which correlates with other studies demonstrating that kinesthetic learning enhance students' engagement and enthusiasm, with students becoming more confident in speaking English as a result [3].

The next possible instance of utilizing kinesthetic learning in the English classroom is applying building, using paper. One of the common themes under study for learners studying English as a second language is housing and living. An approach capable of creating a more engagement- and creativity-stimulating dynamic in the lesson procedure is conducting a task requiring students to build a sample of their preferred type of living space, sticking paper walls, floor and other parts into one complete system, while also naming each of the objects and details as their vocabulary stage of the task, which could be replaced with practicing some grammar rule through creation of a dialogue between fictional characters living in the constructed paper house. Considering that the given exercise may be quite extensive, we suggest conducting this task in a team-oriented form.

Continuing our observation, we took notice that kinesthetic learning may be effective not only for active perception and fixation of the new information and material on the lessons, but furthermore appropriate for teaching students to practice a more efficient team work, if a task is team-oriented.

We proceeded with the use of kinesthetic learning, utilizing a task where students needed to download a mobile app, which allows to add visual make-up products to various individuals' photographs. One may notice that one of the most frequent themes which serve as a basis for learners of English as a second language is a theme on appearances and facial features. The kinesthetic approach to make the given type of lesson more engaging would be to provide students with a task where they are given photographs of various individuals' faces and they have to put appropriate makeup, taking into consideration the facial structure and features of the given people. Working with the apps' tools, imagining the actual makeup application is the kinesthetic angle to this theme.

Combining this task with learning the vocabulary may make the learning process more efficient due to students being actively involved in the process through doing and learning. English teachers can use their creativity to make classes much more original, and go outside the formal bonds of instructing [4].

Needless to mention, that it is not only the principal tasks of the lesson that hold huge importance, but also the preparatory exercises, more widely known as «warm-up tasks». There is a kinesthetic approach to them as well. For instance, a lecturer may provide learners with a task where students are engaged in an interactive physical «warm-up», where students need to perform various exercises as walking, running or jumping, moving to various directions depending on what is being shown on the interactive board in the classroom, while seeing different imaginary conditions of the game as some adventurous or fantasy settings. One may make use of various videomaterials available on a video-sharing platform, YouTube [5].

Continuing observation, we took notice that kinesthetic learning increased students' engagement and motivation for active participation and learning on the lessons, which in result lead to an increase in efficiency of the lessons.

To provide quantitative data, we can demonstrate the results of the conducted post-test after 4 weeks of the use of kinesthetic learning.

Table 5. Results of the post-test

ST1	28
ST2	23
ST3	20
ST4	25
ST5	19
ST6	18
ST7	26
ST8	21
ST9	23
ST10	27
ST11	24
ST12	25
ST13	30
ST14	18
ST15	21
ST16	23
ST17	24
The average number of points	23,23

One may notice the difference in the results of the post-test, with the novel average result being 23,23 points. Combined with observation, we came to a conclusion that the use of kinesthetic learning in the classroom of learning as a second language serves as an effective tool in increasing lessons' efficiency through a more heightened engagement of the students on the lessons. In regards to the actual quantitative distance between the results of the pre-test and the results of the post-test, the increase of 3,35 points may be noticed.

Results

The conducted observation and comparison of the results of the pre-test and post-test of the same students after 4 weeks of utilizing kinesthetic learning in the classroom allows us to infer that application of this approach improves students' involvement and attention on the lessons, which in result leads to an increased productivity and efficiency of their work and learning process.

Recommendations

We recommend studying the issue of the use of kinesthetic learning in the classroom of studying English further. There is no doubt in the efficiency of learning English language through doing, composing and performing – however, the matter needs additional development and discussion.

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